

NORM, NETWORK, AND EDUCATION: SETBACKS IN THE SUS (2008–2024) AND CHALLENGES FOR POPULAR AND DIGITAL HEALTH EDUCATION

NORMA, RED Y EDUCACIÓN: RETROCESOS EN EL SISTEMA ÚNICO DE SALUD (2008-2024) Y DESAFÍOS PARA LA EDUCACIÓN EN SALUD POPULAR Y DIGITAL

NORMA, REDE E EDUCAÇÃO: RETROCESSOS NO SUS (2008–2024) E DESAFIOS À EDUCAÇÃO POPULAR E DIGITAL EM SAÚDE

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Abstract

This study analyzes the reduction of educational actions within Brazil's Unified Health System (SUS) from 2008 to 2024, focusing on the impacts on Popular Health Education (PHE) in Primary Health Care (PHC). The objective is to understand the contradiction between the normative discourse of the National Primary Care Policies (PNAB, 2006; 2011; 2017), which emphasize community education, and the institutional practice marked by a biomedical and productivity-centered logic. A mixed-methods approach was adopted, combining document analysis of the PNABs with quantitative analysis of DataSUS records. Findings reveal a drop of over 90% in educational activities during the period, from 73.5 million to 7.5 million per year, while biomedical procedures exceeded 400 million annually. This disparity highlights an increasing medicalization of care, weakening health promotion practices and community engagement. The low proportion of educational actions (6 per 1,000 consultations) reflects the structural precarization of PHC and the limited integration of emancipatory digital technologies. The study concludes that a paradigmatic shift in PHC is needed, including the replacement of purely quantitative metrics with qualitative assessments, revision of funding criteria to prioritize PHE, investment in communication technologies, and the effective integration of PHE into health professional training. These measures are essential to restore a more humanized, democratic, and transformative approach to care, aligned with the founding principles of SUS.

Keywords: Health Education; Digital Communication; Democratization of Health Services.

Resumen

Este estudio visa analizar la reducción de las acciones educativas en el Sistema Único de Salud (SUS) entre 2008 y 2024, con foco en los impactos sobre la Educación Popular en Salud (EPS) y la Atención Primaria en Salud (APS). El objetivo es comprender una contradicción entre el discurso normativo de las Políticas Nacionales de Atención Básica (PNAB, 2006; 2011; 2017), que valoriza la educación comunitaria y la práctica institucional marcada por una lógica biomédica y productivista. Por eso, adoptamos una metodología errónea, combinando el análisis documental de las PNAB con el análisis

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cuantitativo de datos de DataSUS. Los resultados evidencian que queda superior al 90% de las acciones educativas en este período, pasando de 73,5 millones a 7,5 millones por año, mientras que los procedimientos biomédicos superan las 400 millones al año. Esta disparidad revela un proceso de medicalización del cuidado, enfraqueciendo prácticas de promoción de la salud y la construcción del vínculo comunitario. La baja proporción de acciones educativas (6 por cada 1.000 consultas) refuerza la precarización estructural de la APS y la dificultad de incorporar tecnologías digitales con potencial emancipador. Concluyendo que es necesario reorientar a APS por meio da valorização de avaliações qualitativas, revisão dos critérios de financiamento, investimento em tecnologias comunicacionais e inclusão efetiva da EPS na formação em saúde. Estas medidas son fundamentales para fortalecer un cuidado integral, democrático y humanizado, en consonancia con los principios del SUS.

Palabras clave: Educación para la salud; Comunicación digital; Democratización de los servicios de salud.

Resumo

Este estudo visa analisar a redução das ações educativas no Sistema Único de Saúde (SUS) entre 2008 e 2024, com foco nos impactos sobre a Educação Popular em Saúde (EPS) na Atenção Primária à Saúde (APS). O objetivo é compreender a contradição entre o discurso normativo das Políticas Nacionais de Atenção Básica (PNAB, 2006; 2011; 2017), que valorizam a educação comunitária, e a prática institucional marcada por uma lógica biomédica e produtivista. Para isso, adotou-se uma metodologia mista, combinando análise documental das PNABs com análise quantitativa de dados do DataSUS. Os resultados evidenciam uma queda superior a 90% nas ações educativas no período, passando de 73,5 milhões para 7,5 milhões por ano, enquanto os procedimentos biomédicos ultrapassaram 400 milhões anuais. Essa disparidade revela um processo de medicalização do cuidado, enfraquecendo práticas de promoção da saúde e a construção do vínculo comunitário. A baixa proporção de ações educativas (6 para cada 1.000 consultas) reforça a precarização estrutural da APS e a dificuldade de incorporar tecnologias digitais com potencial emancipador. Conclui-se que é necessário reorientar a APS por meio da valorização de avaliações qualitativas, revisão dos critérios de financiamento, investimento em tecnologias comunicacionais e inclusão efetiva da EPS na formação em saúde. Tais medidas são fundamentais para fortalecer um cuidado integral, democrático e humanizado, em consonância com os princípios do SUS.

Palavras-chave: Educação para a Saúde; Comunicação Digital; Democratização dos Serviços de Saúde.

Introduction

Popular Health Education (Educação Popular em Saúde, EPS) is one of the most powerful and transformative pillars of Brazilian collective health. Grounded in Paulo Freire's principles and rooted in social movements and grassroots experiences, EPS is based on emancipatory practices and the valuing of people's knowledge, proposing the collective construction of care. Since the establishment of Brazil's Unified Health System (Sistema Único de Saúde, SUS), community-based health education has been recognized as a strategy to promote social participation and democratize care, receiving normative support across successive editions of the National Primary Health Care Policy (Política Nacional de Atenção Básica, PNAB).

The history of EPS is intertwined with social struggles for rights—particularly the right to health—and it has been formally incorporated into SUS guidelines as a strategic practice within Primary Health Care (PHC). This recognition was consolidated through Ordinance No. 2,761/2013, which instituted the National Policy on Popular Health Education within SUS (Política Nacional de Educação Popular em Saúde no SUS, PNEPS-SUS). The PNEPS-SUS reaffirms the commitment to universality, equity, comprehensiveness, and effective popular participation in SUS and proposes a political-pedagogical practice that permeates actions aimed at health promotion, protection, and recovery, grounded in dialogue among diverse forms of knowledge (Art. 2). The document further acknowledges that this policy emerges from the historical contributions of grassroots actors and social movements—key protagonists in struggles against marginalization and in the construction of a democratic and popular project (Art. 3, §6).

Beyond the normative framework of the PNEPS-SUS, recent experiences illustrate how social participation can be effectively implemented in the day-to-day work of health services. Costa et al. (2025) report the reactivation of Local Health Councils (Conselhos Locais de Saúde, CLS) led by a multiprofessional residency program in Family Health, showing that educational strategies, dialogue circles, and community mobilization can strengthen social control and bring users, health professionals, and managers closer together.

Thus, EPS is not merely a methodology or educational approach; rather, it constitutes an ethical and political guideline for care that values ancestral knowledge, social participation, and the co-construction of knowledge—strategic dimensions for consolidating PHC as a space of listening, dialogue, and social transformation. Over recent decades, EPS has become a field of symbolic and political dispute, positioning itself against a form of technical rationality centered on medicalization and the fragmentation of care. Through active listening, horizontal dialogue, recognition of subjectivity, and appreciation of territorial cultures, EPS challenges the hegemonic logic of the biomedical model. As Vasconcelos (2001) emphasizes, EPS operates not only as an educational practice but also as a means of reorganizing public health based on listening and commitment to concrete historical subjects.

However, despite its prominence in institutional discourse, a growing gap between policy and practice is evident. Official indicators show a downward trend in health-education actions within territories, while biomedical procedures continue to expand substantially. Between 2008 and 2024, health-education actions recorded in the Outpatient Information

System (Sistema de Informações Ambulatoriais, SIA/DATASUS) dropped from 73.5 million to only 7.5 million annually. In contrast, clinical and care-related procedures exceeded 400 million per year.

This disparity underscores the persistence of a productivity-driven logic centered on quantitative metrics and clinical indicators, which marginalizes care initiatives involving listening, bonding, and social participation. An analysis of the three PNAB editions suggests that, despite references to health education and community protagonism, the emphasis remains on technical and care-related parameters, with requirements focused on productivity, procedural coverage, and disease control.

This hollowing out of educational practices can be understood, in part, through the persistence of institutional dispositifs (apparatuses) of power that regulate users' experiences and shape health professionals' practices. Goldenzweig (2020), for example, shows how the clinical encounter in PHC often normalizes users' speech, translating it into nosologies and protocols that obscure subjective experience. Similarly, Boeff (2019) argues that women's suffering is frequently framed through biomedical diagnoses that silence the complexity of lived experience, reinforcing gender inequalities and moral stigmas. Silva (2020), in turn, highlights how the medicalization of school-related difficulties reflects the hegemony of technical knowledge that disregards social determinants and cultural crossings within communities—a process replicated across multiple fields of health.

In this article, we offer a critical analysis of the trajectory of EPS within SUS, focusing on the marked reduction of community-based educational actions over the past 16 years. We examine the effects of biomedical hegemony on the organization of Primary Health Care (PHC) and the obstacles faced by popular educational practices within prevailing institutional logics. Drawing on secondary DataSUS records, documentary analysis of PNAB documents, and a theoretical review, we reflect on current challenges to consolidating EPS as a structuring practice within PHC. We argue that, in light of the erosion of educational actions, it is urgent to rethink parameters for evaluating quality of care, strengthen funding for educational practices, invest in emancipatory digital technologies, and establish Popular Health Education as a transversal axis in health professional education. This requires reaffirming SUS's political and ethical commitment to autonomy, dialogue, and social participation.

The Place of Popular Education in the PNAB: Ambiguous Presences and Significant Absences

The National Primary Health Care Policy (Política Nacional de Atenção Básica, PNAB), across its three editions (2006, 2011, and 2017), incorporates principles and practices related to health education in uneven ways. Although social participation, the promotion of autonomy, and educational actions recur in the normative discourse, their operationalization varies considerably across the texts, revealing persistent tensions and gaps between discourse and institutionalized practice.

In the 2006 PNAB, Popular Health Education (EPS) does not appear as a named or structured category. Instead, the policy devotes greater attention to Permanent Health Education (Educação Permanente em Saúde, EP), presenting it as a strategy to qualify health workers to implement a new model of care centered on the Family Health Strategy (Estratégia Saúde da Família, ESF). EP is described with a certain degree of methodological density and is linked to efforts to reorganize work processes. By contrast, social participation is invoked in several passages—from the general principles of primary health care (Brazil, 2006, pp. 10–11) to the description of work processes and professional responsibilities (Brazil, 2006, pp. 26 and 42). Terms such as “community participation,” “health education actions,” and “social control” are mentioned, yet without detailing how they should be implemented. Health education appears, for example, among the duties of nursing assistants and technicians (Brazil, 2006, p. 46), but in an operational manner disconnected from pedagogical foundations. As a result, participation is framed in a prescriptive and idealized way, while educational work directed toward the population remains generic, leaving room for vertical, information-based practices.

The 2011 PNAB recognizes the educational dimension as constitutive of care and introduces the notion of territorialized educational actions aimed at strengthening individual and collective autonomy. The document recommends that such actions occur not only within health facilities but also in community settings, such as schools and community halls (Brazil, 2011, p. 7). It also reaffirms the importance of qualified listening and the sociocultural embeddedness of subjects in care processes (Brazil, 2011, p. 8). However, although it aligns with principles that would later be formalized in the National Policy on Popular Health Education within SUS (Política Nacional de Educação Popular em Saúde no SUS, PNEPS-SUS),

approved in 2013, the PNAB does not explicitly link these commitments to a critical and participatory methodological approach. Openness to participation is presented as a normative value, yet it still lacks specific operational instruments for implementation.

Once again, emphasis is placed on Permanent Health Education, which gains both theoretical and operational density. The PNAB devotes a dedicated section to the topic, presenting it as a critical and decentralized pedagogical strategy grounded in the analysis of work and professional learning. A range of practices is highlighted, signaling an intention to move beyond traditional instructional models, as illustrated by the following excerpt:

Permanent Health Education should be grounded in a pedagogical process that encompasses everything from the acquisition and updating of knowledge and skills to learning that emerges from the problems and challenges faced in the work process, involving practices that may be defined by multiple factors (knowledge, values, power relations, planning, and work organization, among others), and that take into account elements that are meaningful to the actors involved [...] (Brazil, 2011, p. 7, author's translation)

In contrast, educational practices directed toward the population remain confined to generic guidelines, with limited emphasis on dialogical methods, participatory planning, or the recognition of community knowledge as a source of knowledge production. Although the policy advances Permanent Health Education—particularly through bottom-up planning and critical analysis of work processes—this methodological density is not extended to community-oriented educational actions to the same degree. This asymmetry between the robustness of worker training and the fragility of educational practices aimed at the population suggests a hierarchical conception of health education, in which technical qualification is prioritized while popular protagonism remains marginal.

The 2017 PNAB marks a more pronounced turning point. The document neither mentions Popular Health Education nor adopts the term “popular education,” signaling a shift away from participatory and dialogical guidelines that had gained ground in earlier formulations. Instead, it adopts a conception of health education centered on information transmission, risk-factor control, and individual behavior change—as reflected, for example, in the emphasis on prevention actions anchored in epidemiological profiles and in clinical, behavioral, and environmental risk factors (Brazil, 2017, p. 22). This biomedical and normativizing approach shifts the focus from collective and participatory action to individual

responsibility, hollowing out the transformative potential of EPS. At the same time, the emphasis on targets, indicators, and the coverage of clinical procedures is reinforced, shaping a managerialized model of care that places limited value on relationships, time for care, and educational work as central components of health practice.

This context is further aggravated by the downgrading of the Family Health Strategy as the priority model, opening space for more flexible organizational forms that are more distant from the territory. This shift further weakens the possibility of contextualized educational practices oriented toward bond-building and qualified listening. The disarticulation between the 2017 PNAB and the National Policy on Popular Health Education (2013) is symptomatic: despite the validity of the PNEPS-SUS and its broad participatory construction, the policy is not even mentioned in the PNAB text, revealing an institutional process of erasure of popular education as a legitimate care strategy within SUS.

In summary, across the three PNAB editions, popular education appears in an ambiguous and increasingly marginal way, even where participatory discourse is present. Social participation, users' autonomy, and educational actions are reaffirmed as structuring principles; however, they lack methodological tools, dedicated funding, and operational guidelines to ensure effective implementation. Meanwhile, Permanent Health Education aimed at health workers gains conceptual density and institutional structure, revealing an asymmetry in how different educational processes are conceived and regulated within SUS.

This gap between normative discourse and institutional effectiveness will be examined in the following sections, drawing on empirical data that highlight the contraction of educational actions in territories and the challenges faced by workers who seek to sustain practices of listening, bonding, and shared care amid the biomedical and managerialist hegemony of contemporary Primary Health Care.

The Contradiction in the Data: Decline of Educational Actions and the Rise of Biomedical Logic

The analysis of DataSUS records from 2008 to 2024 clearly exposes the gap between institutional discourse and everyday practice in Primary Health Care (PHC). Over just over 15 years, educational actions recorded in the Primary Care Information System (Sistema de

Informação da Atenção Básica, SIAB/SISAB) declined from 73.5 million to approximately 7.5 million annually. This reduction—exceeding 90%—points to a systematic contraction of dialogical and community-based practices in the routine work of health services, particularly those related to health education.

Over the same period, biomedical procedures in primary care increased sharply, surpassing 400 million records per year. The ratio between educational actions and consultations is even more alarming: in 2024, for every 1,000 medical consultations, only six educational actions were recorded. These figures suggest not merely a statistical trend but a structural reconfiguration of the care model, which prioritizes indicator-driven control and the reproduction of technical procedures at the expense of comprehensive, participatory, and emancipatory care.

This shift should be interpreted in light of the ambiguity across the three PNAB editions, which points to normative fragility regarding Popular Health Education (EPS). Although popular education is acknowledged in the 2006 and 2011 PNAB documents, its presence is marginal and weakly specified in methodological terms; the 2011 edition advances in valuing listening practices and territorial approaches but does not articulate EPS as an explicit guideline; and the 2017 edition represents a regression, making no reference to EPS and reinforcing information-based actions tied to biomedical targets.

Thus, the DataSUS figures do not merely document a downward trend; they condense the practical effects of this normative absence. As Vasconcelos (2001) and Silva (2020) emphasize, the growing emphasis on targets and measurable productivity—typically expressed through consultations, tests, and prescriptions—subjects both clinical practice and management to technocratic and medicalizing logics. Educational practice, in turn, is symbolically and institutionally downgraded, becoming increasingly invisible within evaluation and financing systems that shape everyday health-service work.

This silencing and exclusion of educational practices can also be understood as a form of biopolitical disciplining. Biopolitics, as analyzed by Foucault, operates in subtle and continuous ways, organizing and regulating people's lives through institutional norms and regimes of knowledge. In health and education, this logic is expressed through the promotion of behaviors deemed healthy and productive, grounded in medical-scientific knowledge that

defines what is correct or desirable. Within this context, health education becomes an instrument of social control, oriented more toward the normalization of bodies and behaviors than toward the emancipation of subjects (Foucault, 1988, pp. 125–136).

By devaluing community knowledge and marginalizing participatory approaches, the system privileges vertical educational practices centered on information transmission and the correction of individual behaviors. This reinforces a logic in which the population is trained to comply rather than to engage in dialogue or transform its reality. It is an exercise of power that presents itself as care but, in practice, disciplines subjects—regulating ways of living and thinking in the name of health and social order.

In this sense, by replacing dialogue and listening with prescriptive actions, care is reconfigured as an intervention upon individual bodies, detached from context and subjected to protocols. As Goldenzweig (2020) notes, this logic directly affects the subjectivity of both workers and users, who may come to internalize an understanding of health centered on obedience and normalization rather than autonomy and co-authorship.

Boeff's (2019) critique further illuminates this scenario: health systems tend to recognize only what they are able to measure. Practices such as bond-building, the strengthening of autonomy, and shared care—central to EPS—become disposable within official instruments, producing a cycle of invisibilization that undermines their political and methodological sustainability.

Finally, the gradual transformation of PHC in recent years has also redefined the role of medical authority, making it a key component of a system that values prescribing and target attainment over listening and encounter. Programs such as *Previne Brasil* have intensified this movement by linking funding to the delivery of individual biomedical actions, thereby hollowing out the collective and educational dimensions of care. Medical authority, historically associated with technical expertise, is increasingly called upon to function as an interface of the managerial apparatus—operating systems and delivering numbers rather than cultivating bonds.

This reconfiguration of medical practice distances what Merhy (1998) conceptualizes as “living labor in action” from the everyday reality of PHC. In this context, clinical practice ceases to be a space of invention and welcoming and becomes a site for the reproduction of norms. As Foucault (1988) reminds us, disciplinary power operates diffusely through the

normalization of gestures, time, and bodies. In contemporary PHC, this normalization occurs through the imperatives of metrics, control, and efficiency.

The consequences are twofold: on the one hand, the verticalization of relationships between professionals and users; on the other, the progressive illness and burnout of health workers themselves, especially those who identify with the principles of collective health and popular education. Within this model, medical authority becomes a burden: it demands performance while obstructing listening; it requires technical presence while disauthorizing care as an ethical, shared experience.

Although the 2017 PNAB reveals the hollowing out of educational practices and the predominance of clinical indicators, experience reports such as Costa et al. (2025) suggest that local interventions can, at least in part, circumvent these institutional constraints. The reactivation of Local Health Councils by PHC residents indicates that structured and participatory educational actions can challenge hegemonic biomedical logics and narrow the gap between policy and practice.

Breaking with this trend requires reclaiming EPS as a structuring axis of PHC, in line with the National Policy on Popular Health Education within SUS (PNEPS-SUS, 2013). This entails not only expanding its normative recognition but also revising the management, financing, and evaluation instruments that currently regulate the production of care. Ultimately, it requires contesting the very meaning of authority in health: whether it will function as an instrument of control or emancipation, and whether it will serve the machinery—or life itself.

Proposals for an Epistemological Turn: From Procedure to Encounter

In view of the shrinking of educational practices and the deepening of biomedical logics in Primary Health Care (PHC), it is urgent to propose an epistemological turn that reinstates Popular Health Education (EPS) as a structuring axis of care. This turn is not limited to the addition of new technical guidelines; rather, it requires transforming the foundations that sustain management, training, financing, and evaluation practices within SUS. The challenge is to shift the center of gravity of public policy—currently shaped by quantitative indicators and procedural targets—toward encounter among forms of knowledge, subjects, and territories. For EPS to become a structuring axis of PHC, it is essential to learn from

concrete experiences. Costa et al. (2025) show that integrating residents, users, and managers within Local Health Councils can enable not only information sharing but also co-authorship, the strengthening of bonds, and the fostering of community protagonism—core principles of EPS and Freirean pedagogy.

A first step is to review the evaluation models used in PHC, moving beyond the hegemony of biomedical indicators and incorporating qualitative dimensions that frame care as a relational process. Assessing the quality of health work should include criteria such as longitudinal bonding, users' autonomy, listening capacity, and popular participation in decision-making. Approaches such as participatory evaluation, the analysis of clinical narratives, and the use of dialogue circles as evaluative devices point to viable alternatives. These strategies can capture ethical and subjective dimensions of care that current information systems render invisible, thereby contributing to the democratization of evaluative processes.

Second, PHC financing criteria should be reformulated to effectively value educational actions and Permanent Health Education processes. The current financing model linked to *Previne Brasil* reinforces prescriptive practices focused on measurable, short-term results. Such a logic discourages bond-building and intersectoral work, which require time and attentive listening. A financing policy that recognizes and remunerates EPS actions—such as groups, workshops, dialogical home visits, community task forces, and the training of health councilors—is essential to rebalance the relationship between the technical and the popular, between numbers and meaning.

The third line of action concerns health professional education, which must break with the “banking” model of teaching and incorporate Popular Health Education as method, content, and stance. Inspired by Paulo Freire, this approach entails recognizing the other as a subject of knowledge and the territory as a pedagogical space. EPS should not be treated as a peripheral topic but rather as a transversal axis across undergraduate education, residency programs, and continuing professional education. Horizontal dialogue, critical problematization of reality, and an ethical-political commitment to the social determinants of health must be reclaimed as foundational elements of training within SUS. Education that does not transform tends to reproduce the very system that produces illness.

Finally, this epistemological turn requires expanding and strengthening the communication technologies used in PHC to enhance channels of dialogue between health teams and communities. This includes digital tools (e.g., messaging platforms, community podcasts, and local radio) as well as ancestral forms of collective communication, such as storytelling circles, the Theatre of the Oppressed, and artistic practices rooted in the territory. These technologies should not be reduced to their instrumental function; rather, they should be understood as mediators of bonds and promoters of autonomy. They can create symbolic spaces where speech circulates and experiences of care are collectively re-signified.

Together, these four directions—qualitative evaluation, ethical financing, dialogical education, and technologies of listening—point to possible paths for reversing the current hollowing out of educational practices and reclaiming the transformative power of Popular Health Education. The epistemological turn proposed here is not merely technical but political and ethical: it seeks to place life back at the center of public policy, subverting a logic of performance in favor of a logic of encounter. Such a task requires institutional courage, collective commitment, and openness to relearning from the territory. As Freire reminds us, no one educates anyone else, nor does anyone educate themselves alone; people educate one another in communion (Freire, 1987, p. 39, author's translation).

Final Considerations

The analysis presented in this article reveals a contradiction that has shaped Primary Health Care (PHC) over recent decades: on the one hand, a normative discourse that affirms the centrality of social participation, shared care, and the territory as a living space for the production of health; on the other, institutional practices that reinforce a biomedical, technicist, and productivity-driven logic, capturing clinical work and care through indicators, targets, and procedures detached from lived realities. This split is not merely discursive but also epistemological, political, and ethical. It produces a field of action under tension, in which emancipatory practices such as Popular Health Education (EPS) are progressively hollowed out or reduced to superficial, information-based, and vertical forms.

This distortion of SUS's founding project—within which EPS stands as one of the most powerful pillars of transformation—highlights the urgent need for a paradigm shift in PHC. This is not simply a matter of restoring visibility to popular education, but of restructuring the

very modes of management, evaluation, and health professional education around a different point of reference: encounter, listening, co-authorship, and the valuing of popular knowledge as the foundation of care. This entails breaking with the hegemony of instrumental rationality and opening space for ways of knowing and doing guided by an ethics of implication, horizontal dialogue, and the collective construction of solutions in the everyday life of territories.

In this context, EPS can no longer be treated as an accessory, an appendix, or a complementary strategy. It must be recognized as a strategic axis of PHC, capable of challenging medicalizing practices and fostering processes of subjectivation, autonomy, and participation. Strengthening EPS means reanimating the political soul of SUS, offering an antidote to the ethical hollowing out produced by management policies that prioritize performance over bonds, data over meaning, and prescription over care.

Accordingly, we propose the following directions for continuity: qualitative research on successful EPS experiences in territories; evaluative methodologies sensitive to the subjective and relational dimensions of care; training reforms grounded in Freirean pedagogy; and strengthened spaces of co-management among workers, managers, and users, where listening and the negotiation of meanings can effectively guide health actions.

We therefore conclude that the epistemological turn required in PHC is not merely technical or administrative, but profoundly political. It is through disputes over meanings, values, and practices that the future of SUS will be defined: whether it will remain an instrument for the control and regulation of life, or whether it will reinvent itself as a field of care, emancipation, and living democracy.

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